

Estimating the Cost of Heterogeneous Solutions

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Abstract — Existing estimation methods have severe limitations when it comes to estimating the delivery cost of heterogeneous IT-based solutions. In this experience report we present Solution-Based Estimation, a new approach that explicitly links a solution’s architecture to its delivery cost model.

Keywords — *Solution Architecture, Solution Costing, Solution Based Estimation, Estimation Methods*

I. INTRODUCTION

Most estimation and metrication methods assume a certain level of homogeneity across the system for which the cost is estimated. Such homogeneity is required to be able to extrapolate and re-use measurements made on smaller or previous, comparable versions of a system. IT services organizations like CGI¹ increasingly design and deliver enterprise-level solutions that consist of multiple substantially different software, infrastructure and often organizational elements, integrated to deliver a coherent set of services. For such heterogeneous solutions, the assumption of homogeneity does not hold, and existing estimation methods cannot be used directly.

In order to estimate the delivery cost of heterogeneous IT-based solutions, the solution must be broken down into constituent elements that by themselves are homogeneous enough to reliably identify and apply appropriate existing estimation methods for each element. In this experience report, we describe the approach that we have developed within CGI to estimate such heterogeneous solutions in a consistent way, which we call Solution-Based Estimation.

II. SOLUTION-BASED ESTIMATION

Enterprise-level solutions are delivered by integrating a wide variety of components, among which can be:

- Bespoke software applications.
- Software embedded in hardware and firmware.
- Many flavors of Commercial Off-The Shelf (COTS) software, such as platform and utility software, Operating Systems, databases, web-servers and middleware, but also large enterprise resource planning packages that require extensive configuration.

- IT infrastructure, such as servers, storage, network elements, connections and associated tools.
- Services to manage software and infrastructure, or to perform business processes based on the IT, e.g. in Business Process Outsourcing.
- Organizational entities that use the software and infrastructure to deliver the IT services.

We call such enterprise-level solutions consisting of very different components *heterogeneous IT-based solutions*. Accurately estimating the cost of delivering such heterogeneous solutions requires that the estimators not only look at *what* the solution does (“on the outside”), but also at *how* it does it: its internal structure and the interaction between its constituent elements. We call this internal structure the solution architecture, and the role that designs this structure the solution architect. Research shows that applying solution architecture practices is indeed correlated with higher accuracy of budget prediction and lower expected budget overruns [1].

Our Solution-Based Estimation approach is based on:

- Strong involvement of the solution architect in the estimating process.
- The presence of a documented solution architecture as input to the estimate.

We will explore these principles in the following two sections.

III. SOLUTION BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE

In our Solution-Based Estimation approach, the part of the architecture documentation that serves as key input to the estimating is called the Solution Breakdown Structure (SBS). The SBS is a hierarchical decomposition into deliverable elements at the appropriate level of granularity. The SBS looks like a tree, and the right level of granularity of the leaves of the tree is mostly determined by the required ability to estimate the cost of delivering and integrating that element. This ability depends on:

- Size and homogeneity of the deliverable element: it should be either small enough for a reliable conventional estimate, or homogeneous enough to be able to apply metrics-based estimation techniques.

¹ CGI is a global IT and business process services provider delivering business consulting, systems integration and outsourcing services.

Figure 1 Artifacts and roles in solution based estimating

- Delivering organization: most enterprise-level solutions are delivered by multiple, co-operating organizational entities (e.g. software development teams, hardware vendors, infrastructure management teams, subcontractors). As a rule of thumb, a single deliverable leaf entity on the SBS tree should be delivered by not more than one organizational entity.

The SBE approach contains guidance for the identification, validation and documentation of the lowest level deliverable elements. Of course, adding up the estimated costs of the various deliverable elements in the SBS does not yet yield a complete estimate of the solution’s delivery cost: for that we also need to consider the cost of integrating the various elements into a coherent solution, as explained in the next section.

IV. ROLES IN SOLUTION-BASED ESTIMATION

Figure 1 shows the relationship between the various artifacts in our Solution-Based Estimation approach, and the roles responsible for their creation.

In the top left area in the figure, we see a simplified representation of the solution architecting work, for which the solution architect is responsible. A solution is designed to fulfill a business goal, which is elaborated into a set of functional and non-functional requirements. The functional requirements describe *what* the solution should do, and the non-functional requirements (often called –ilities or quality requirements) describe *how well* it should perform its task: how fast, how reliable, how secure, etc. Based on these requirements, the solution architect designs a target solution and an architecture, using an appropriate solution architecture approach such as RCDA [2]. Part of the documentation of this target solution’s architecture is the solution breakdown structure (SBS), as described in the previous section.

At the bottom of Figure 1 is a representation of the work of the project or delivery manager involved. The manager selects an appropriate high-level delivery strategy for the solution, in close cooperation with the architect, using the target solution

architecture as input. Apart from an overall project lifecycle for the integral solution, this involves selecting fitting realization methods for each class of deliverable elements in the architecture; this can be as trivial as “buy the specified server”, or as critical as “select a software development lifecycle” of “hire the required staff”. The delivery strategy also specifies how the various deliverable elements are integrated into a coherent solution.

The next artifact produced by the project/delivery manager is the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). This is a structured list of activities needed to deliver the solution. The activities are derived from the deliverable elements in the solution breakdown structure, and from the delivery strategy. For example, if the solution breakdown structure contains a piece of software that needs to be developed, the delivery strategy prescribes the software development lifecycle to be used, resulting in activities like detailed design, coding and testing for that specific software element. The effort involved in each activity can then be estimated using either metrics-based or expert estimating techniques.

Adding the time dimension to the WBS yields the planned project schedule. This also requires knowledge of the architecture, specifically knowledge of the dependencies between deliverable elements and their preferred integration order.

Once the schedule is drafted, the costing model can be derived from it, achieving the goal of Solution-Based Estimation. For complex costing models, some organizations assign this activity to a specialized cost engineer role.

The direct arrow between the SBS and the costing model in Figure 1 represents the option to directly translate delivery elements from the SBS into costing model elements. This option exists for deliverable elements whose delivery costs can reliably be estimated without elaborating them into a WBS and delivery schedule. This is the case for elements for which a sizing parameter (like *capacity* for hardware or *functional size* for software) can reliably be converted to a cost estimate, based on e.g. metrics or known prices.

The costing model is the final artifact of Solution-Based Estimation: a cost estimate for a heterogeneous solution.

V. COMPARISON WITH OTHER APPROACHES

Using a system's architecture in the cost estimating process is key to be able to account for the impact of non-functional requirements in the costing model. This is due to the fact that the non-functional requirements or quality attributes are the primary driver for the architecture of software-intensive systems [3]. The architecture represents the way the non-functional requirements are addressed in the solution, and thus the cost of the architecture represents the cost of the non-functional requirements. In estimating methods based purely on functional size like function points or use case points, the impact of the non-functional requirements and the architecture is accounted for in a multiplication factor that depends heavily on the architecture; that factor can only be re-used in other estimates if the architecture is comparable. In all other cases, the cost estimate should explicitly include the system's structure or architecture to account for non-functional requirements.

Software estimating methods like COCOMO [4] and Cosmic [5] take system structure into account through structural elements like internal interfaces or lines of code. These methods, however, can only be applied if all structural elements consist of software, and if the software in these elements is reasonably homogeneous in terms of complexity, technology, etc. None of these conditions hold in the type of heterogeneous solutions in scope in this paper, where the deliverable elements can be infrastructural or organizational in nature, and where software elements can come from various sources, using different technologies.

The use of a Solution Breakdown Structure and Work Breakdown Structure in estimating was adapted from the PRINCE2 project management methodology [6]. The PRINCE2 version of the SBS is called the Product Breakdown Structure (PBS). In PRINCE2, it is used mostly as a scope definition tool from the project manager's point of view. We have adapted it to work as part of the architecture documentation, and renamed it to Solution Breakdown Structure to reflect that adaptation.

VI. CONCLUSION

Although architecture is often seen as a separate domain, architecture and estimation are strongly related. The Solution Based Estimation approach provides a structured way of linking the architecture of heterogeneous IT-based solutions to delivery cost. We are in the process of spreading the use of Solution Based Estimation practices in various CGI business units. It is too early for a formal validation of the approach, but based on anecdotal evidence we are starting to see:

- Better scope definition, leading to more detailed underpinning of estimates.
- Fewer interpretation differences regarding the solution design and its impact on planning and budget.

- Improved awareness of the economic impact of solution design among solution architects and management.
- Improved traceability from estimated costs to solution requirements (both functional and non-functional).
- Better consolidation of partial estimates of solutions' constituent elements.

Given this early anecdotal evidence, we expect Solution-Based Estimating to substantially improve the accuracy of cost estimation for heterogeneous solutions.

VII. REFERENCES

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